

An elastoplastic constitutive model to simulate the non-linear behaviour of chitosan material for nerve regeneration guide tubes applications

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Abstract

Neurotmesis is the most severe injury a peripheral nerve can endure. One of the strategies to treat this type of nerve injury is the tubulization technique, consisting of bridging the two nerve tips enclosed by a tube made of a compatible biomaterial. Chitosan scaffolds is one of the most popular (and successful) solutions used for the tubulization technique. After implanting the chitosan tube, it will experience mechanical stimuli due to natural movements, inducing strain-stress states in the biomaterial. It is relevant to characterize the mechanical behaviour of chitosan scaffolds in order to improve the structural design of chitosan tubes. First, in this work, it is proposed an elastoplastic constitutive model to predict the nonlinear behaviour of chitosan scaffolds in both compression and tensile conditions. Then, using the data available from experimental tests documented in the literature, the most relevant mechanical properties for the proposed elastoplastic constitutive model were retrieved, allowing the construction of phenomenological laws for each required mechanical property. The proposed phenomenological law is capable to provide the Young's modulus, the tangent modulus and the yield stress (in both compression and tensile states) as a function of the degree of deacetylation.

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1 Introduction

Every year, there are more than 500.000 new cases of peripheral nerve injuries worldwide due to traumatic events. It is a major cause of morbidity and life-long disabilities and it represents approximately 3% of all trauma patients [1, 2, 3]. There are different causes for injuries in the peripheral nervous system, being the most common direct mechanical trauma and surgical resection secondary to tumour excision [4]. The peripheral nervous system is composed of motor, sensory and mixed nerves. The cell bodies of peripheral nerves are located in the spinal cord and the long cytoplasmic extensions that transmit electrical signals to target organs are called axons [5]. As it is shown in Figure 1, different layers of connective tissue encase peripheral nerves both internally and externally. The epineurium protects and nourishes the nerve fascicles, which are surrounded individually by a layer of connective tissue called perineurium. This layer provides tensile strength to the nerves. Inside each fascicle there is a loose connective tissue matrix called endoneurium that protects and nourishes each axon [6, 7]. Schwann cells surround axons with a membrane of myelin with interposed spaces called nodes of Ranvier, where the saltatory propagation of action potentials occur [8].

Contrarily to what happens in the central nervous system, the peripheral nervous system is able to regenerate after a nerve lesion in the presence of a suitable environment, and to recover some of the lost functions [1, 4, 9, 10]. However, the

Figure 1: Representation of the cross-sectional area of a peripheral nerve

regenerating capacity and the recovery outcome are dependent on some factors such as the age of the patient, the length and type of injury, the quality of the repair technique, and the proximity of the injury to the nerve cell body [4, 9, 10, 11].

1.1 Types of injuries

Seddon [12] and Sunderland's [13] classifications are typically used to define the different types of injuries based on their response. Seddon's classification is based on the architecture of the nerve and its ability to transmit nerve signals [6]. Later on, this classification was expanded by Sunderland and depending on the severity, it divides peripheral nerve injuries into five grades [13]. Neurapraxia (grade 1) is the mildest form of nerve injury and it is related to a block in the fiber conduction due to nerve stretching or compression [8, 14]. It results in temporary motor paralysis, with or without sensory loss. Although demyelination occurs, the structural integrity is preserved since the epineurium, perineurium and endoneurium remain intact, allowing for a full nerve recovery [8, 15]. As a more severe injury, axonotmesis (grade 2) brings more tragic consequences such as complete motor, sensory and autonomic dysfunction. In this case, the structural integrity of the surrounding support structure of the nerve is also preserved, even though the axon suffers some damage and the endoneurium remains intact. As for the recovery rate, it is slow and may be incomplete [6, 14, 15]. The most severe injury is known as neurotmesis (grade 3/4/5), ranging from transection (with intact perineurium) to a completely transected nerve, where there is the total interruption of the structural integrity of the support structure of the nerve [14, 15]. This prevents the occurrence of spontaneous recovery and leads to complete motor, sensory, and autonomic dysfunction [15]. These neurotmetic injuries require surgical intervention while neurapraxia and axonotmetic injuries can be treated by conservative methods [6, 8, 16].

1.2 Nerve repair strategies

Being neurotmesis the most severe injury a peripheral nerve can endure, this work only focused on the strategies currently implemented to treat this type of nerve injury. These strategies can be divided into two categories: bridging, using grafting and tubulization techniques, and end-to-end suturing of the nerve stumps [2, 11]. The latter can only be performed in small nerve gaps (<5 mm), where a tension-free coaptation between the proximal and distal nerve stumps is possible. Otherwise, the regrowth of the nerve fibers will be impaired [17, 18, 19]. Also, it has become more apparent over the years that a purely surgical strategy does not address all the molecular and cellular events which occur during the regeneration of the peripheral nerve [4]. On the other hand, bridging nerve gaps of critical length in humans, which are over 3 cm, using an autologous nerve graft (autograft) remains the gold standard for repairing non-suturable peripheral nerve injuries [9, 17, 20, 21]. However, some disadvantages are associated to this technique, such as the need for a second surgery to harvest the nerve graft, and consequent sacrifice of a healthy nerve, the mismatch in size, and the neurological morbidity at the donor site, which makes it a non-optimal strategy [2, 9, 10, 22]. Moreover, because of the unavailability of motor nerves, autografts are primarily obtained from sensory nerves. This is a drawback when it comes to grafting sensory or mixed nerves and may be another reason to explain the poor functional recovery rates associated to autografts [19]. Over the years, an effort has been made in order to develop biomaterials that can be used as substitutes of autografts, including natural and synthetic polymers [22]. These biomaterials, which affect the final outcome, can be easily modified to provide an optimized environment for peripheral nerve regeneration [9, 17]. Some tissue engineering strategies are focused on increasing the ability of these nerve guidance channels to guide and sustain axon regeneration, overcoming the nerve gap limitation

Figure 2: Chemical structure of chitin (a) and chitosan (b)

[9, 23, 24]. They can assume different forms, being that hollow tubes are the clinically approved alternative to autografts, and are sutured between the proximal and the distal nerve stumps. These nerve guidance channels create a more favourable environment and allow to reach better regenerative results when comparing with autografts [2, 9, 19, 22]. Nowadays there are some FDA-approved nerve guidance channels commercially available, such as NeuraGenTM, NeurotubeTM and NeurolacTM [9, 25]. Although they avoid donor site morbidity and have an unlimited supply, they also have limitations when it comes to supporting peripheral nerve regeneration and the consequent functional outcomes [1, 19]. These hollow tubes can only be used for small diameter nerves, such as digital nerves, and for nerve defects up to 2-3 cm in length, which leaves the majority of patients with peripheral nerve injuries out of the scope [2, 9, 10, 24, 26]. From these limitations arises the need to construct a nerve guidance channel made from a biomaterial, which has already demonstrated good results in peripheral nerve regeneration and that performs better than autografts in larger nerve gaps. The process of choice of this material must be well considered since the use of different materials and fabrication techniques leads to variable physical properties. One of these materials is chitosan, which has been used as a scaffold to help in the peripheral nerve regeneration process. It can assume many shapes and forms and this variability leads to a set of very different physical, biological and chemical properties that will ultimately influence the results concerning nerve regeneration.

1.3 Chitosan

Although many different biomaterials have been used to construct neural scaffolds, for the past years chitosan has been considered a preferable candidate for peripheral nerve regeneration. It derives from chitin, which is a structural element found in the exoskeleton of crustaceans, and it can be obtained by N-deacetylation of chitin [9, 27], Figure 2(a). This polymer is a linear polysaccharide composed of glucosamine and N-acetylglucosamine units which are linked by $\beta(1-4)$ -glycosidic bonds [28, 29, 30], Figure 2(b).

Chitosan has a set of characteristics that make it a viable choice as a biomaterial for the construction of nerve guidance channels. Some of these characteristics are its facile chemical modification and excellent reproducibility, which enables it to be applied in medicinal, drug delivery, tissue engineering, and other industrial fields [27, 30, 31, 32]. As a natural polymer, chitosan is regarded as non-toxic and biologically compatible, being that it promotes cell adhesion and proliferation [1, 22, 30, 32]. It also presents an excellent antibacterial and antifungal activity, biodegradability and a film-forming ability [11, 31, 33]. Several studies have demonstrated that chitosan is a good option for neural tissue engineering and more specifically that chitosan tubes promote the repair of the peripheral nervous system [9, 11, 17, 22]. Chitosan nerve guidance channels can undergo surface modification in order to provide guiding and structural cues for growing axons and they can also be constructed as interconnected-porous structures by freezing and lyophilizing methods [17, 34]. In its pure state, chitosan can take many forms that can differ between them on the degree of deacetylation, which is represented by the ratio between glucosamine and N-acetylglucosamine units [28, 35, 36]. The degree of deacetylation is one of the most important properties of chitosan and it allows to differentiate it from chitin considering the amount of free amino groups (NH_2) [28, 37, 38]. During the process of deacetylation of chitin, an acetyl group ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$) is removed from its molecular chain, leaving behind an amino group [38]. Thus, when a polymer molecule consists of more than 50% of N-acetylglucosamine units it is known as chitin. The one with more than 50% of N-glucosamine units becomes soluble in aqueous acidic solutions and is known as chitosan [29, 39]. The degree of deacetylation is determined by the conditions selected for the deacetylation process and generally it ranges from 50% to 90–95% [11, 37, 40]. Moreover, for biological applications, chitosan can be further deacetylated, reaching a degree of deacetylation higher than 95% [38]. The degree of deacetylation influences the physical, chemical and biological properties of this polymer, such as cell response, crystallinity, solubility, and the tensile strength of chitosan films [37, 41]. Considering for example solubility, when the degree of deacetylation is below 70% it

becomes difficult to dissolve chitosan in acetic acid solutions, which makes it harder to fabricate chitosan conduits [23]. Another parameter that varies with the degree of deacetylation is the degradation rate. Several studies have confirmed that highly deacetylated chitosan scaffolds (> 85%) have a lower degradation rate, meaning that they may last in vivo for several months [28, 30, 34, 40]. Therefore, when considering a peripheral nerve injury, the goal is to develop a chitosan nerve guidance channel that maintains its physical structure long enough to ensure nerve regeneration since it takes the proximal regenerating nerve stump several weeks to reach the injured distal nerve stump [29, 42].

1.4 The biomechanical behaviour

In order to facilitate the use of chitosan scaffolds for peripheral nerve repair, one must take into account the biomechanical behaviour of the peripheral nerves. The stresses to which nerves are exposed under physiological conditions must be analysed in order to understand how these scaffolds should behave after implantation so they can better play their role as nerve regeneration enablers. Peripheral nerves are subjected to mechanical stresses, which are defined as the applied external forces divided by the cross-sectional area over which they act. They can be applied as tensile, compressive, shear stress or triaxial stress state [43]. Many in vitro and in vivo studies have demonstrated that peripheral nerves behave as non-homogeneous, viscoelastic tissues and present non-linear stress-strain characteristics when subjected to tensile forces [44]. Tension tests can be performed in order to determine the mechanical properties of nerves, whose mechanical behaviour can be described by a stress-strain curve. Experimentally, an increasing uniaxially tensile load can be applied to the specimen, which will deform until a fracture occurs [43, 45]. These loads can be applied perpendicularly or in parallel to the length of the nerve causing transverse or longitudinal stress, respectively. Thus, in physiological conditions, when the nerve bed (defined as the tract formed by the structures that surround the nerve) is elongated due to joint motion, the nerve is placed under increasing tensile stress and it will elongate and glide [43, 46]. In this case, the elongation of the nerve will cause an increase in nerve strain, which will be greater in the nerve segment closest to the moving joint. In other cases, where a tensile stress is applied, peripheral nerves initially present a low elastic modulus that gradually increases with increasing strain until reaching a maximal value [43, 44]. The tolerance to stretching of peripheral nerves can go up to 6 – 8% of their total length without undergoing morphological and functional changes. On the other hand, further stretching (> 15%) leads to a complete block of intraneural flow [47]. Under physiological conditions, chitosan scaffolds have low mechanical strength and are unable to maintain a predefined shape for transplantation, which limits their use as nerve guidance channels in clinical applications [9, 22, 32, 33, 48, 49]. Also, because the conduits may compress the regenerating nerve, they may not be able to maintain their physical structure until the injury is healed. This occurs because chitosan is more brittle and rigid than nervous tissue [50]. Determining the mechanical properties of chitosan nerve guidance channels is crucial for they allow to predict their performance in the physiological environment, including their influence on specific cell functions. For example, a balance between strength and flexibility must be found when planning the ideal mechanical characteristics of the nerve guidance channels since they have to be able to hold the nerve in place after being implanted [51, 52]. Chitosan scaffolds can be characterized via compression testing in order to obtain their compressive modulus and/or strength [28]. These values reported in the literature range from 0.0038 MPa to 2.56 MPa for the compressive elastic modulus and from 0.059 MPa to 0.125 MPa for the compressive strength (or ultimate compressive stress) [32]. Scaffolds that do not exhibit any apparent pores can have an elastic modulus from 5 to 7 MPa. These values change whenever a degree of porosity is added to the scaffolds, which decreases both the elastic modulus and the mechanical strength [29]. Soft biomaterials with a low Young's modulus are the preferable candidates when it comes to mimicking the mechanical properties of nerves [50]. There are several factors that influence the mechanical properties of chitosan scaffolds, such as the pore size and orientation, the degradation rate, and the degree of crosslinking [34, 39]. Some technologies and strategies have been upgraded in order to improve the mechanical properties of chitosan scaffolds, which should lead to better outcomes considering nerve regeneration. Crosslinking these scaffolds by the addition of a reinforcement agent, incorporation of a synthetic polymer or complexing with another polymer, are some of the methods that improve the mechanical properties of chitosan and also decrease the degradation rate [32, 48]. This makes chitosan scaffolds less susceptible to the enzymes responsible for their degradation [53]. However, the concentration of added crosslinker agent must not be too high or the biological properties of the chitosan scaffolds might be impaired. For this reason, non-crosslinked chitosan is often chosen for biomedical applications [32].

2 Elastoplastic constitutive model

The literature shows that structures made of chitosan present a nonlinear behaviour when submitted to external uniaxial loads [54, 55]. Linear behaviour is followed by a yield plateau before rupture is reached. It is observed that if the yield stress

is reached and the applied load is removed, chitosan specimens experiment permanent and non-recoverable deformations. Thus, in this work, it is proposed to numerically reproduce the behaviour of chitosan material using an elasto-plastic formulation. First, in order to capture the nonlinear behaviour of an elastoplastic material it is necessary to define the mathematical law for the plastic component of the deformation. Thus, three aspects must be considered: a yield criterion (permitting to analyse the beginning of the plastic regime and indicating the stress level in terms of the stress tensor); a flow rule (defining the relationship between stress and deformation after plastification); and a hardening law (describing if, and how, the yield criterion depends on the plastic deformation) [56]. The yield criterion permits to define the beginning of the plastic regime. Usually, a yield criterion can be formulated as: $F(\sigma, \kappa) = f(\sigma) - \sigma_Y(\kappa) = 0$. The yield criterion allows to define the beginning of the plastic regime. The yield criterion $F(\sigma, \kappa)$ depends on the stress tensor σ and on the hardening parameter κ . Notice that the yield criterion expression allows to define the triaxial stress state, σ , as a scalar function, $f(\sigma)$. It is the scalar value from $f(\sigma)$ that will be compared with the material yield stress $\sigma_Y(\kappa)$, obtained experimentally. If the stress state at a material point exhibits $f(\sigma) > \sigma_Y(\kappa)$, it means that the point shows an elastic behaviour, governed by the linear equations of the theory of elasticity [57]. Instead, if $f(\sigma) \leq \sigma_Y(\kappa)$, it indicates that the point is yielding. The modified Hill's yield criterion is most suited when the material exhibit anisotropy in its plastic behaviour and asymmetry in its yield-stress behaviour [29]. This means that the yield function is able to describe the behaviour of materials with different compressive and tensile yield stresses. The mathematical law for the criterion is represented in equation 1, [29].

$$\left(F \cdot (\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + G \cdot (\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2 + H \cdot (\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + 2 \cdot L \cdot \tau_{yz}^2 + 2 \cdot M \cdot \tau_{zx}^2 + 2 \cdot N \cdot \tau_{xy}^2 \right)^{0.5} + I \cdot \sigma_{xx} + J \cdot \sigma_{yy} + K \cdot \sigma_{zz} = 1 \quad (1)$$

The parameters F, G, H, L, M, N, I, J and K are determined experimentally, representing the current state of anisotropy of the material. Considering the material plastically isotropic the value of the material parameters is given by

$$F = G = H = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_0^t + \sigma_0^c}{2 \cdot \sigma_0^t \cdot \sigma_0^c} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$I = J = K = -\frac{\sigma_0^t - \sigma_0^c}{2 \cdot \sigma_0^t \cdot \sigma_0^c} \quad (3)$$

$$L = M = N = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_0^t + \sigma_0^c}{2 \cdot \sigma_0^t \cdot \sigma_0^c} \right)^2 = 3F \quad (4)$$

Since the plastic flow is associated with the yield criterion, in this work an associated flow rule is considered - the Prandtl-Reuss flow rule – which defined the plastic strain rate as,

$$d\epsilon_{ij}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} = d\lambda \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (5)$$

Notice that $d\epsilon$ is the plastic rate multiplier and $\mathbf{a}$ is the flow vector, normal to the adopted yield function, $f(\sigma)$. Thus, the flow vector can be presented as,

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} = \left\{ \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{xx}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{yy}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{zz}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{xy}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{yz}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{zx}} \right\}^T \quad (6)$$

Following the linear elastic generalised Hooke law, the following relation between the stress rate $d\sigma$ and the elastic strain rate $d\epsilon_e$ is assumed:

$$d\sigma = \mathbf{D} \cdot d\epsilon_e = \mathbf{D} \cdot (d\epsilon - d\epsilon_p) \quad (7)$$

in which $d\epsilon$ is the total strain rate and $d\epsilon_p$ is the plastic strain rate. Matrix $\mathbf{D}$ represents the material elastic constitutive matrix,

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{xx}} & -\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_{yy}} & -\frac{\nu_{zx}}{E_{zz}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_{xx}} & \frac{1}{E_{yy}} & -\frac{\nu_{zy}}{E_{zz}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{xz}}{E_{xx}} & -\frac{\nu_{yz}}{E_{yy}} & \frac{1}{E_{zz}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{xy}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{yz}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{zx}} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Where E_{ii} is the Young modulus in direction i , ν_{ij} is the Poisson ration and G_{ij} is the shear modulus, with respect to directions i and j . Assuming the associated flow rule and considering that the yield surface only depends on the magnitude of the applied principal stresses and of a hardening parameter, equation 7 be rewritten as,

$$d\sigma = \mathbf{D} \cdot (d\varepsilon - d\lambda \cdot \mathbf{a}) \quad (9)$$

Since the stress must remain on the yield surface in order to occur plastic flow, the following has to be verified,

$$dF = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)^T d\sigma - \frac{\partial \sigma_Y}{\partial \kappa} d\kappa = \mathbf{a}^T \cdot d\sigma - A \cdot d\lambda = 0 \quad (10)$$

being A an hardening parameter that depends on the hardening rule [56], defined by,

$$A = \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \sigma_Y}{\partial \kappa} d\kappa \quad (11)$$

Applying equation 9 into equation 10,

$$d\lambda = \frac{\mathbf{a}^T d\varepsilon}{A + \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{a}} \quad (12)$$

Introducing the value of $d\lambda$ into equation 5, the plastic strain rate can be written as,

$$\varepsilon^p = \partial\lambda \cdot \mathbf{a} = \frac{\mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot d\varepsilon}{A + \mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a}} \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (13)$$

and then, consequently, using equation 7, it is possible to write the stress rate as,

$$d\sigma = \mathbf{D} \cdot \left(d\varepsilon - \frac{\mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot d\varepsilon}{A + \mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a}} \cdot \mathbf{a} \right) = \left(\mathbf{D} - \frac{\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D}}{A + \mathbf{a}^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{a}} \right) \cdot d\varepsilon = (\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D}_{ep}) \cdot d\varepsilon \quad (14)$$

Matrix $\mathbf{D}_{ep}$ represents the elasto-plastic constitutive matrix. Since the work hardening hypothesis is employed [56] considering the associated flow rule, it is possible to define explicitly the hardening parameter A . Thus, because chitosan $\sigma - \varepsilon$ experimental curves can be adjusted to a linear elastic-linear plastic hardening model, the hardening parameter A can be defined as in [56], i.e.,

$$A = H'(\bar{\varepsilon}_p) = \frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{d\bar{\varepsilon}_p} = \frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon - d\varepsilon_e} = \frac{1}{\frac{d\varepsilon}{d\sigma} - \frac{d\varepsilon_e}{d\sigma}} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{E_t} - \frac{1}{E}} = \frac{E_t}{1 - \frac{E_t}{E}} \quad (15)$$

Notice that E and E_t represent the elastic modulus and the tangential modulus in the reference direction and corresponding stress state (tensile or compression), respectively. In order to build a nonlinear solution procedure, the material behaviour can be modelled in the form of an incremental relation between the incremental stress vector and the strain increment. The "backward-Euler" procedure [58] is considered to force the stress to return to the yield surface. The nonlinear solution can be obtained using the several variations of the Newton-Raphson non-linear solution method, as described in the literature [59]. One of the simplest variations, the initial stiffness method combined with an incremental solution, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Newton-Raphson non-linear solution method, assuming the initial stiffness method combined with an incremental solution.

Figure 4: Relationship between the tensile elongation at break (a) and the tensile strength (b) with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan in a tensile state.

3 Phenomenological laws

This work proposes a constitutive material model to allow the prediction of the nonlinear elastoplastic behaviour of chitosan. Experimental tests documented in the literature were studied and gathered [43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 55], and the most relevant mechanical properties for the proposed elastoplastic constitutive model were retrieved. The acquired data allowed to construct the figures presented in this section, and consequently, build the proposed phenomenological laws. The mechanical properties found were obtained by analysing the stress-strain curves documented in the mentioned literature, or by directly assuming the values proposed by their authors.

Both the yield criterion and the corresponding yield surface are considered. The model respects a flow rule defining the relationship between stress and deformation after the plasticity point, and a hardening law that describes if, and how, the yield criterion depends on the plastic deformation. For this, it is important to obtain the mechanical properties of chitosan, such as Young's modulus (E), the yield stress (σ_Y) and the strain for both compression and tension tests. In the compression test, it is also possible to obtain the tangential Young's modulus (E_t). These isotropic material properties were related with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan, which importance was explained previously. Therefore, assuming the nonlinear elastoplastic behaviour of chitosan and resorting to the literature, it was possible to obtain these mechanical properties and to analyse how they vary with the degree of deacetylation. The literature shows that when in tension, the curve representative of the relation between breaking elongation and the degree of deacetylation of chitosan depicts a second-order polynomial behaviour. Thus, when constructing the curves relative to the strain both in the elastic and elastoplastic limits, it was considered the same second-order polynomial behaviour. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the variation of the mechanical properties of chitosan with its degree of deacetylation in a tensile state. These properties include the tensile elongation at break (ϵ_u^t) (or the ultimate tensile strain), Figure 4(a), the tensile strength (σ_u^t) (or the ultimate tensile stress), Figure 4(b), the tensile Young's modulus (E^t), Figure 5(a), and the tensile elastic limit strain (ϵ_0^t), Figure 5(b). In Figures 4(a) and (b) and in Figure 5(b), the trend line followed a second-order polynomial behaviour, while in Figure 5(a) it followed a linear behaviour.

The following equations describe the behaviour of the curves presented in Figures 4 and 5.

$$\epsilon_u^t = -0.1127 \cdot d_d^2 + 18.882 \cdot d_d - 735.87, \quad \text{in } [\%], \quad \text{with } R_{\epsilon_u^t}^2 = 0.5769 \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_u^t = -0.0122 \cdot d_d^2 + 2.2457 \cdot d_d - 95.516, \quad \text{in } [MPa], \quad \text{with } R_{\sigma_u^t}^2 = 0.9718 \quad (17)$$

$$E^t = 0.5558 \cdot d_d - 33.747, \quad \text{in } [MPa], \quad \text{with } R_{E^t}^2 = 0.9063 \quad (18)$$

$$\epsilon_0^t = -0.0008 \cdot d_d^2 + 0.1274 \cdot d_d - 4.6255, \quad \text{in } [\%], \quad \text{with } R_{\epsilon_0^t}^2 = 0.5376 \quad (19)$$

Being d_d the degree of deacetylation, in [%], and R^2 the correlation coefficient of the corresponding approximation curve. Notice that with ϵ_0^t and E^t it is possible to estimate the elastic limit stress: $\sigma_0^t = E^t / \epsilon_0^t$.

In Figures 6, 7 and 8 are represented the variations of the mechanical properties of chitosan with its degree of deacetylation

Figure 5: Relationship between the tensile Young's modulus (a) and the tensile elastic limit strain (b) with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan in a tensile state.

Figure 6: Relationship between the compression elastic limit strain (a), the compression elasto-plastic limit strain (b) with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan in a compressive state.

Figure 7: Relationship between the elastic limit stress (a) and the elasto-plastic limit stress (b) with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan in a compressive state.

Figure 8: Relationship between Young's modulus (E) with the degree of deacetylation of chitosan in a compressive state.

in a compressive state. These properties are the compressive elastic limit strain (ε_0^c), Figure 6(a), the compressive elastoplastic limit strain (ε_u^c) (or the ultimate compression strain), Figure 6(b), the compressive elastic limit stress (σ_0^c), Figure 7(a), the compressive elastoplastic limit stress (σ_u^c) (or the ultimate compression stress), Figure 7(b), and the compression Young's modulus (E^c), Figure 8.

Such as in the case of the tensile state, the following equations and correlation coefficients describe the behaviour of the curves presented in Figures 6, 7 and 8.

$$\varepsilon_0^c = -0.0519 \cdot d_d^2 + 8.617 \cdot d_d - 347.4, \quad \text{in } [\%], \quad \text{with } R_{\varepsilon_0^c}^2 = 1.00 \quad (20)$$

$$\varepsilon_u^c = -0.5643 \cdot d_d^2 + 93.668 \cdot d_d - 3795.9, \quad \text{in } [MPa], \quad \text{with } R_{\varepsilon_u^c}^2 = 1.00 \quad (21)$$

$$\sigma_0^c = 0.033 \cdot d_d - 2.4899, \quad \text{in } [MPa], \quad \text{with } R_{\sigma_0^c}^2 = 1.00 \quad (22)$$

$$\sigma_u^c = 0.1109 \cdot d_d - 8.3199, \quad \text{in } [\%], \quad \text{with } R_{\sigma_u^c}^2 = 1.00 \quad (23)$$

$$E^c = 0.6738 \cdot d_d - 51.088, \quad \text{in } [MPa], \quad \text{with } R_{E^c}^2 = 1.00 \quad (24)$$

Again, d_d represents the degree of deacetylation, in [%], and R^2 is the correlation coefficient of the corresponding approximation curve. Although it is possible to obtain the Young's modulus for a compressive state directly from equation 24, it is also possible to obtain the same variable using the values from equations 20 and 22. Thus, following the schematic figure 9, it is possible to understand that all the parameters required to build the bi-linear elastoplastic constitutive model can be obtained with equations 16 to 24. The tensile and compression Young's modulus (E^t and E^c , respectively) can be obtained with:

$$\begin{cases} E^t = \frac{\sigma_0^t}{\varepsilon_0^t} \\ E^c = \frac{\sigma_0^c}{\varepsilon_0^c} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The tangent elastic modulus, E_T^t and E_T^c for tensile and compression cases, respectively, can be calculated with:

$$\begin{cases} E_T^t = \frac{\sigma_u^t - \sigma_0^t}{\varepsilon_u^t - \varepsilon_0^t} \\ E_T^c = \frac{\sigma_u^c - \sigma_0^c}{\varepsilon_u^c - \varepsilon_0^c} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Figure 9: Schematic stress-strain tensile-compression curve.

4 Conclusion

Being a nonlinear material, chitosan behaves differently when being compressed or tensioned. When subjected to a compressive force, chitosan presents a clear elasto-plastic behaviour, which can be simulated using an elasto-plastic model. On the other hand, chitosan presents a slight ductile behaviour (almost brittle) when subjected to a tensile force. Nevertheless, it can also be represented with an elasto-plastic model. The degree of deacetylation was shown to have a marked effect on the physicochemical properties of chitosan films. Higher degree of deacetylation chitosan films showed a greater crystallinity, a higher elastic modulus and tensile strength and a lower swelling index than those with lower degree of deacetylation [23]. The relationship here established between different mechanical properties of chitosan and its degree of deacetylation can be adapted to the crystallinity and swelling index of chitosan. With the development of this constitutive model, it is now possible to obtain the different mechanical properties of chitosan for both conditions: compression and tension, as functions of the degree of deacetylation. Combined with advanced discretisation techniques, such as the finite element method or meshless methods, the proposed constitutive model will allow to perform computational simulations capable to predict the non-linear response of chitosan scaffolds, or other chitosan-made structures, under mechanical solicitations. Since computational simulations are less expensive than experimental trials, this numerical approach will contribute to reduce the total cost associated with the research of new geometries of chitosan tubes for the regeneration of the peripheral nerve.

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